

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of
accessible IT systems and tools

PROJECT

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools

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Report: Diagnoses' spectrum in LIVE IT

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1 DIAGNOSES' SPECTRUM IN LIVE IT

1.1 MAKERSPACE AND HACKATHONS

Throughout the reports and deliverables of the LIVE IT project descriptions of participants in the project activities, many disabilities were addressed and described. Most of the participants in the makerspace do not register or inform if they are a Person with Cognitive Disabilities, an expert or professional in the field, or simply as someone who has interest in the field, therefore this kind of data is not available or collected as regards to the Makerspace.

As far as the Hackathons are concerned, a total of 38 teams / participations in 5 Hackathons, come from:

Origin	Teams
Ireland	5 teams
UK	7 teams
Portugal	11 teams
Greece	14 teams
Design for All Europe	1 team
	38 teams

The allocation of teams' participation in the 5 Hackathons is as follows:

Hackathon	Teams
1 st Hackathon	6 teams
2 nd Hackathon	9 teams
3 rd Hackathon	12 teams
4 th Hackathon	4 teams
5 th Hackathon	7 teams
	38 teams

In terms of teams, countries and diagnosis participating in the Hackathons the data is as follows:

Greece

Hackathon	Country	Team	Diagnosis
1	Greece	EEEEK	Down syndrome, motor skills disabilities
1	Greece	AMEN organisation	Dementia, Alzheimer, Aged related Cognitive decline
1	Greece	EPSEP Ioannina	Dementia, mild cognitive impairment
1	Greece	Promesip	Experts, researchers
2	Greece	AMEN organisation	Dementia, Alzheimer, Aged related Cognitive decline

2	Greece	Promesip EEEEK	Experts, researchers
3	Greece	Alexandreias	Down syndrome, motor skills disabilities
3	Greece	Promesip	Experts, researchers
3	Greece	EPSEP Ioannina	Dementia, mild cognitive impairment
4	Greece	EPIONI	ADHD
5	Greece	AMEN organisation	Dementia, Alzheimer, Aged related Cognitive decline
5	Greece	NIMIA	Experts, researchers

Portugal

Hackathon	Country	Team	Diagnosis
1	Portugal	ADFP	Cognitive Deficit, ADHD, ASD
2	Portugal	ADFP	Cognitive Deficit, ADHD, ASD
2	Portugal	CECD	Intellectual Disability
2	Portugal	CBN	ASD, ADHD, Anxiety, Intellectual Disability
3	Portugal	ADFP	Cognitive Deficit, ADHD, ASD
3	Portugal	CECD	Intellectual Disability
3	Portugal	CBN	ASD, ADHD, Anxiety, Intellectual Disability
4	Portugal	ADFP	Cognitive Deficit, ADHD, ASD
5	Portugal	CBN	ASD, ADHD, Anxiety, Intellectual Disability

Ireland

Hackathon	Country	Team	Diagnosis
1	Ireland	2 nd Level student	Dyslexia
2	Ireland	University students	ADHD, Dyslexia
3	Ireland	NUIG access centre, FIT ICT talent pipeline and Dyslexia Ireland	Experts
4	Ireland	Special education teachers	Experts
5	Ireland	3 rd level students	Dyslexia, ASD and ADHD

UK and EIDD

Hackathon	Country	Team	Diagnosis
2	UK	Bristol co-creation lab participants	Dyslexia, ADHD, ASD

3	UK	Bristol co-creation lab participants	ASD, Dyslexia, ADHD, Learning Difficulties
3	UK	Neurodiversity Learning	Dyslexia, ASD, Learning Difficulties, ADHD
4	UK	Bristol co-creation lab participants, SCT and A2ndVoice plus	ASD, Dyslexia, Dissociative Seizures, Dyspraxia, Age Related Cognitive Decline, Stroke recovery, Irlen Syndrome, Down's syndrome
5	UK	Individual	PwCD (IT Expert)
5	UK	Bristol co-creation lab participants	Dyslexia, ADHD, ASD
5	EIDD	Working Group	PwCD, a web designer and a web developer

Total Numbers per Diagnosis

Diagnosis	Frequency	Ap. Persons
ADHD	16	36
Age Related Cognitive Decline	4	10
Alzheimer	3	9
Autism Spectrum Disorder	15	32
Anxiety	5	14
Cognitive Deficit	4	12
Dementia	5	16
Dissociative Seizures	1	3
Down's syndrome	3	8
Dyslexia	8	19
Dyspraxia	1	2
Intellectual disability	5	17
Irlen Syndrome	1	2
Learning Difficulties	2	6
Mild cognitive impairment	2	7
Motor skills disabilities	2	3
Stroke recovery	1	2
Total	78	198

1.2 CO-LABS

The following graph shows the range and representation of different diagnoses of participants in the LIVE IT project activities.

Diagnoses

